

SPEECH DEVELOPMENT TECHNOLOGIES IN SPASTIC FORMS OF CHILDREN'S CEREBRAL PALSY

Abdumutalibova Yoqutxon Ikromjon qizi

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

Faculty of special pedagogy and inclusive education

Speech therapy, 2nd year Master's student

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Abstract

the study of the speech of children with speech defects in the article. Methods of developing independent speech in stuttering children, conducting a conversation with a speech therapist, educator and parents. Examination of independent speech in children who stutter. Improvement and classification of the development of independent speech of stuttering children is described.

Key words: ontogenetic development, specific sex and age characteristics, alalia, aphasia, rhinolalia, neurotic stuttering, neurotic stuttering, cognitive, cognitive and affective aspects, genetic, social and personal factors, diagnostic and correction processes, phonetic, lexical and grammatical tools.

The development, prospects, well-being, spiritual growth of every country, becoming one of the most developed countries in the world depends on young people who are educated, have high intellectual potential, and embody good qualities in their hearts and minds, and are mature and perfect in all respects, the destiny of the Motherland. To bring up a devoted, faithful generation, to raise the quality and content of education to the highest levels, first of all, it is an honorable and at the same time responsible task for teachers and educators.

As the Republic of Uzbekistan moves towards building a legal democratic society, it pays special attention to the development of its citizens, especially the growing young generation, which is determined to build a new society. Organization of perfect personality education has been an important requirement and main goal of social society in all eras. Of course, even in the conditions of current education reforms, they are talking about the education of the perfect generation: "The future of our country, the tomorrow of our people, the reputation of our country in the world community is the most important thing for our children to grow up, grow up, and become human beings. depends on penetration." - they emphasized.

The first stage of the development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is characterized by a number of changes: preschool education was formed as an open educational institution; the most important

function of preschool educational institutions is to protect children's vital activities and strengthen their health; successful preparation of children for school education, etc. Also, today in our Republic there are preschool educational institutions of various types (nursery, kindergarten, kindergarten-primary school, state-owned and private).

The responsibility of providing early education to the youth of our country has been assumed by preschool educational institutions that are currently operating in our country. Training is the form of imparting knowledge in pre-school educational institutions. In the course of the training, the child's speech develops, its grammatical and phonetic aspects are polished, and its psychological and intellectual aspects develop as well as its language richness.

Currently, higher demands are placed on the development of the speech of children of preschool age. Meeting these demands requires new research on speech development. Thus, at the current stage of pedagogic science, there are conflicts between the requirements for the development of the speech of older children of preschool age and the implementation of these requirements.

External (exogenous) and internal (endogenous) factors, as well as external conditions of the environment, are distinguished among the causes of speech disorders in children. An evolutionary dynamic approach is used to consider various causes of speech impairment. It consists of analyzing the process of occurrence of the defect, taking into account the general laws of anomalous development and the laws of speech development at each age.

The principle of the unity of biological-social processes in the formation of mental (at the same time speech) processes allows determining the influence of the speech environment, behavior, emotional communication and other factors on the development of the speech system. Children with normal hearing are brought up by deaf and dumb parents, children who are chronically ill and frequently treated in hospitals do not develop speech, long-term mental trauma in the family and bilingualism are the causes of stuttering in children. is an example of the negative impact of the specific environment on the development of speech.

All speech disorders are divided into two groups according to their origin:

1. Speech disorders of an organic nature.
2. Speech disorders of a functional nature. The above-mentioned reasons, in some cases, their combination can lead to the violation of different aspects of speech.

Early detection of the development of various speech disorders is of great importance. If a speech defect is detected for the first time when a child comes to school, then difficulties in correcting it will be observed and it will have a negative effect on learning.

Children love the game so much that they want to play it. But at first they don't know how to do it, and when they do, they don't start. It is known from historical sources that moons, especially folk moons, performed several tasks in the development of a child's personality. First of all, the formation of the correct pronunciation in the child was achieved by reciting expressive stories by heart, adjusting stories in self-initiations. Secondly, he taught him to count, speak quickly, and memorize riddles quickly.

According to the theory of special education, it is very common to divide the games organized for speech-impaired children in the process of speech therapy into two groups: creative games and games with rules. The content of creative games is invented by children and they reflect their impressions, understanding of existence and relations to this month.

Elements of lexical-grammatical and phonetic-phonemically underdeveloped elements are observed in the speech. Children can communicate with people when they have speech, but they do it with the help of parents (educators) and with the help of their specific explanations. At III level of speech underdevelopment:

Games with rules are created by adults and introduced into children's lives. Regular games are determined depending on their content and age of children. Most of the regular games are based on folk games. Many of these regular games have been passed down from generation to generation and have reached us.

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